

MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF MEDIEVAL BUILDING MATERIALS OF CENTRAL ASIAN ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract. This article tells about the construction of a residence in the Middle Ages, its improvement, construction methods and urban planning traditions. At the beginning of the 9th-13th centuries, on the territory of Uzbekistan, the residences of rich and prosperous citizens consisted of an inner and outer courtyard, and rooms were formed around the courtyard. In such dwellings, kitchens, verandas, living rooms, corridors, utility and utility rooms stood out. Below is the detailed information about them.

Key words: ancient rooms, outer yard, inner yard, middle ages, residence.

By the 4th century, frequent attacks by nomadic Turkic tribes on Central Asia led to the decline of the Kushan kingdom. The transition to a new formation accelerated even more during the period when the Hephthalites, and later the Turkic Khanate, subjugated the lands of Central Asia to their power. During the period of the Hephthalites and the Turkic Khanate, a number of independent city-states existed in Central Asia.

and these kingdoms did not become dependent on the Hephthalites or the Khaganate, but limited themselves to paying tribute to him and recognizing their sovereignty. During the period of the Hephthalites and the Turkish Khanate, Khorezm, Tokharistan, Sogd (Sogdion) were their main

had land. Especially Sogd, located on the eastern and western caravan routes, was culturally and economically high. It is connected with Iran, Byzantium, India, the countries of the Far East, as well as with Eastern Europe through Khorezm.

conducted trading activities. Samarkand, considered the largest principality of Sogd, occupied a special place in the social and cultural life of Central Asia and had a strong influence on other kingdoms. Thus, the beginning of the Middle (V-VIII) centuries is characterized as the period of the formation of feudalism in Central Asia, and therefore in historical and scientific literature it is called the period of early feudalism. Together with the above-mentioned cities, Sugdiana, Chaganiyan, Tagoristan, Shosh and Fergana were built during this period.

A number of prestigious cities were also founded. Among them were very famous ancient Samarkand, ancient Penjikent and the cities of Kushaniya, which were considered the capital of the state of Sugdiyana. According to Arab tourists, historians and geographers, most of the cities of Central Asia in the early Middle Ages consisted

of three parts. One of these three parts is the city arch (kohandiz) - the residence of the ruler.

and the second - Shahrison (including Medina), the main part of the city includes shopping malls, other public and residential buildings. The third part was called the discount and formed a trading zone outside the city. But the cities of the VII-VIII centuries.

the results of the study show that most of them consist of only two parts - the ark (or castle) and the city.

According to the Chinese priest Xuanzang, who passed through Samarkand in the 30s of the 7th century, the length of the city wall was 20 meters, it was about 10 kilometers and approximately equal to the size of Morocco at that time. Alexander the Great. .

According to M. Pachos, one of the researchers of ancient Samarkand, the building of the city during the period of early feudalism consisted of three parts. The fortress part of the city rests along the Siyob stream on the north side and is surrounded by defensive walls 1.5 km long. The second part of the city is located to the south

and consists of the residences of the nobility and public buildings. The third part, rabad, was located outside the fortress walls and did not have defensive walls. In the 6th century the city expanded to the south.

will be surrounded by a second defensive wall. The city is intensively developing along its canals. This thing was also considered characteristic of Balkh and Termez. During this period, according to Xuan Zang, fire worship also existed in Samarkand.

Buddhism also developed. That is why in the city, among the houses and other civil buildings, there are religious buildings related to these two religions - fires, sanctuaries equipped with dates and idols, temples, huts.

existed. The total area of Afrosiab is 230 hectares, and layers of the 5th-6th centuries are found throughout its area. Among them, as a well-studied one, one can distinguish a complex of buildings located in the central part of the city, which was originally called the "palace complex", and now the "district of influential families". In 1965-1968, a complex consisting of several rooms was excavated between the second and third ring defensive walls of Afrosiab (subsequently, the excavations were significantly expanded). The mural was found in a multi-room hotel in the center of this complex. Based on the plot of the painting and the Sogdian inscription written on the hem of the man's vest in these paintings, it is assumed that the buildings belong to the Samarkand king (Ikhshidi) Varkhuman. The building is located on the western side of a small building (next to the paved path). The entrance part is bad though a relatively

small part of it has survived. It can be assumed that it was built as a porch due to the presence of two side walls and its orientation to the east.

It can be assumed that it was built as a porch due to the presence of two side walls and its orientation to the east. A path (two doors) from the porch leads to a corridor in the form of a corridor. In the central part of the corridor there is a three-arch tapering door (perspective arch) located on the inner side of the wall.

It leads to a square hotel measuring 11.20 x 11.20 meters. In the four corners of the hotel, at a distance of 2.5 meters, there are traces of four pillars supporting the ceiling of the room. A single seating area is made, surrounded by four inner walls. Walls and platform made of mud bricks and straw

created. Wall paintings were also found in the ruins of Penjikent, Bolalik-Tepa, Varakhshi, Er-Kurgan and many other cities of the 5th-8th centuries.

It is known that Bukhara was a large city in the era of early feudalism. According to L. I. Rempel, the city, located near the Bukhara arch, was crossed by two streets facing the four sides of the sky. Two gates Ark (Registan and Goriyan) and Attaron (Benu Saad), Mihra (Benu Assad), Ark, Hoki Shah-Ristan

It had six gates called Roh, Nur and Shahrstan. The city is crossed by the stream Rudi-zar (Shahrud). According to Narshakhi, near this moat there was a market of sellers of dates (butsotars) and their big temple. Considering the arch area of 3.5 hectares, we see that the city is relatively large. There is information about its location in the Shakhristan region, where the canal flows. During this period, new architectural ideas appeared in Central Asian architecture - the period of late antiquity and early feudalism (U-U centuries). Fortresses of feudal lords, fortresses of wealthy nobles in the city and outside the city were created and updated. Rovali and, which are widely included in his practice

Domed buildings, roofs, windows and doors brought the spirit of a new era to the urban landscape. Castles are unique aspects of early feudal architecture.

this was also noticeable in the construction of buildings. These palace-fortresses arose somewhat apart from the former artistic and cultural centers, mainly as residences of peasant feudal lords. These fortresses are surrounded by strong walls. Around these castles, settlements and markets appeared. Over time, these lands were surrounded by a thick wall. This is how the first feudal cities were formed. In these places, medieval cities arose, where crafts and trade revived.

There are many such addresses on the territory of Uzbekistan, located on the Great Silk Road. The monuments of this period under study include castles and palaces in the oases of Zerafshan, Kashkadarya, Ferghana, Khorezm, and Tashkent.

For example, Oktepa near Tashkent, Teshik castle in Khorezm, Varakhsha near Bukhara differ from each other in their appearance and decoration, but they all have a common similarity based on the great style of the period. Castles, palaces, natural or artificial pyramidal hills were built. To build a palace on such a high platform, to avoid natural disasters and floods, to live a peaceful life, to be able to defend against enemy attack and attack

based on The fact that the outer walls of the palace were strong and high, it was considered necessary to provide this protection and peace. On the outer side of the palace, the decoration is scarce and serious, the surface of the walls of some palaces is made of gopher (kungular) and three-toothed decorative plates, antefix and relief rosettes are used on the upper part of the wall. Particular attention was paid to the interior decoration of the palaces. The rooms are decorated with frescoes and sculptures. 2-3-story arched buildings are located around a large room with a dome or dome, or around an idol-shaped narrow corridor (corridor). In the decoration of the building, various forms that appeared in the previous period, including the Kushan kingdom, generally under the influence of Hellenistic art, such as Ionic currency, ancient capitals, acanthus forms, were almost eliminated or completely reworked, and their appearance was updated. Yunusabad octave in Tashkent

It was one of the castles built around the city in the early Middle Ages and ended its life after the Arab invasion. This feudal fortress served as an administrative center and warehouse for storing food and weapons. There was also a Zoroastrian temple here.

Ak-Tepa Castle is also built on an artificial hill, its thick wall is simple and elegant.

was unfinished. Teshik Castle in Khorezm was also built on an earth embankment. However, its defensive walls have a peculiar corrugated outer finish, in addition to them, there are perspective arches, decorative tiles, and the upper part of the wall is decorated with a frieze. Varakhsha The Palace of Bukhara Khudots (rulers) near Bukhara is a magnificent example of early feudalism. Built on an artificial hill, the outer walls of this palace are corrugated.

has a rich frieze on the upper side of the wall. The gates of the palace are also made in large forms in a festive spirit. The top of the wall is decorated with three-toothed plate half-marks, the walls are decorated with rosettes, the interior of the palace is extremely rich. Sculpture, painting and applied decor

works of art served to make the interior of the palace extraordinarily beautiful and cheerful. According to information, the palace of Al-Fir of the Khorezm king Afrig was also luxurious. It has two floors, and the rise to the second floor is carried out with

the help of special lifting devices- ramps. In early medieval works, including the period of the Ephthalite kingdom, fortified castles, feudal fortresses, and especially

The material evidence that has come down to us and the view of the castle preserved in the wall paintings also confirm the wide distribution of the palaces and the fact that they are an important architectural monument of that period. Similar scenes are found in Panjikent wall paintings, images on the surfaces of copper and silver vessels.

For example, a silver plate depicting "Refining the Fortress" kept in the Hermitage depicts a view of the fortress. The monumental memory of Kesh architecture and palace art had a huge impact. m. frieze, wall corrugation, giving a semi-marked and decorative shape to the top of the roof, their

The interiors and corridors are richly decorated with patterns and thematic paintings, round sculptures and reliefs, which found their expression in later architecture. During this period, the Eagle Castle and Earthen Castles in Khorezm became even more luxurious.

It is enriched with paintings of Khorezm kings, the market square and the city synagogue are enriched with the spirit of the era.

Speaking about the architect of the period of the Turkic khanate, we can say that this khanate came to Central Asia at a time when it developed or began to rise to a new stage of development. The art of the Khakhan period, including its architecture, was associated with the development of the traditions of the Ephtalite period. During the period of the Khaganate, feudal castles and palaces, noble houses in the city and outside the city continued their development as a continuation of the traditions of the previous period.

During this period, Buddhism, Zoroism, Christianity and other religions existed in various colors, as well as the language and customs of the people and the people of the Khaganate. At the same time, the peaceful life and independent life of the local nobility contributed to the formation of original local features in architecture, fine and applied arts. This feature is reflected in the monuments of art and memory of Sogd, Khorezm, Fergana, Kuva Yettisoy. With the development of feudal relations, the old types of cities changed and new types of cities began to appear. If the cities in the era of slavery

correctly and in many cases was characterized by the correct arrangement of quarters, now the first feudal cities are surrounded by strong walls, and the interior is randomly built houses, narrow, crookedly filled with chalar. The 2-3-storey houses of the rich gave a peculiar silhouette to the buildings of the feudal city. Attention was

drawn to the fact that the residences of the kings in the palace and outside the city were luxurious and beautiful. In most cases, a column, semi-column, arch and various decorative architectural volumes are built on an artificial hill. Used to make the royal palace beautiful and majestic. These buildings are also built of raw brick and straw, the walls are finished with ganch, decorated with frescoes and patterns. The special charm of the building was given by ganch, woodcarving and relief images. we are in ruins

The remains of these palaces, which arrived in the 9th century, new types of buildings and creative ideas appeared in the architectural art. In Central Asia, Islam not only strengthened, but also began to develop scientifically.

There are new types of buildings. Such materials as brick, alabaster, ganch were widely used in construction. The construction of hotels and parks has changed the face and topography of the city. City life has moved to Rabod. It's noisy and crowded

markets appeared. Communities of artisans began to form near the shopping streets. The environs of Shahristan became crowded, urban culture spread widely. An important part of Shahristan is the administrative apparatus, the governor's palace, a prison, the mosque was built and serves as the center of the city.

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